

Total numbers and infinity

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Abstract. This paper shows how the infinity of natural, rational and irrational numbers can produce a real contradiction. Contradiction that is formalized by defining a new mathematical tool: the total numbers.

Keywords: infinity, natural numbers, integer numbers, rational numbers, irrational numbers, cardinal numbers, total numbers

1 Introduction

In the initial part of this paper the total numbers are introduced, whose purpose is to extend the notion of number of elements of a set, acting in place of the cardinal numbers.

Then the contradiction we come across in hypothesizing that the integer, rational and irrational numbers are infinite is shown. This contradiction will be formalized by the total numbers previously defined.

The paper concludes with a brief explanation of why cardinal numbers, unlike total numbers, are not able to grasp the contradictory nature of the infinity.

2 Total number

The intuitive principle behind the introduction of total numbers can be called the substitution principle. This is the principle according to which two sets have the same number of elements if and only if the ones can replace the others without changing the sizes involved.

Having said that, let us move on to the following definition:

Definition 2.1. *we define the total number of a set as the ordinal number [1] whose totality of the elements (and therefore the totality of the ordinal numbers that precede it) taken individually and in an ordered manner are able to replace the totality of the elements of that given set.*

For example, if we take the following set D :

$$D = \{a, b, c\}$$

and then the following ordinal number 3:

$$3 = \{0, 1, 2\}$$

we immediately realize that we can use all the ordinals 0,1,2 contained in it to replace all the elements of D . With this, we establish that the ordinal number 3 is also the total number of the set D :

$$\text{tot}(D) = 3$$

If we use the ordinal number 2 instead:

$$2 = \{0, 1\}$$

we realize that we cannot use all the ordinals 0, 1 contained in it to replace all the elements of set D . In fact, although we can replace the two elements a, b we cannot replace element c . With this, we establish that the ordinal number 2 is not the total number of set D :

$$\text{tot}(D) \neq 2$$

Using the ordinal number 4 instead:

$$4 = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$$

we realize that we cannot use all the ordinals 0,1,2,3 contained in it to replace all the elements of set D . In fact, even though we can use the ordinals 0,1,2 we cannot use the ordinal 3. With this, we establish that the ordinal number 4 is not the total number of set D :

$$\text{tot}(D) \neq 4$$

3 Infinity in the case of integer numbers

Theorem 3.1. *The set \mathbb{Z} of integers cannot have an infinite number of elements.*

Proof. Let's take a set A whose elements are obtained by gathering in pairs the elements of set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$, the set of non-zero natural numbers.

A possible set A that can be constructed is the following:

$$A = \{(1, 2), (3, 4), (5, 6), \dots, ([2 \cdot n] - 1, 2 \cdot n), \dots\}$$

where n is a generic non-zero natural number, and where the pairs:

$$\begin{aligned} &(1, 2) \\ &(3, 4) \\ &(5, 6) \\ &\dots \end{aligned}$$

that constitute the individual elements of the set A include the natural number $2 \cdot n$, the double of each element n belonging to the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$, and the natural number $[2 \cdot n] - 1$ that precedes it:

$$([2 \cdot n] - 1, 2 \cdot n)$$

More simply we can write the set A in the following way:

$$A = \{([2 \cdot n] - 1, 2 \cdot n) \mid n \in \mathbb{N}_{>0}\}$$

Let's now put the even numbers of set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ and the pairs of numbers of set A in which that value appears on the right in a one-to-one correspondence:

$$\begin{aligned} 2 &\leftrightarrow (1, 2) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between 2 and 2} \\ 4 &\leftrightarrow (3, 4) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between 4 and 4} \\ 6 &\leftrightarrow (5, 6) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between 5 and 6} \\ &\dots && \\ (2 \cdot n) &\leftrightarrow ([2 \cdot n] - 1, 2 \cdot n) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between } (2 \cdot n) \\ &&& \text{and } (2 \cdot n) \end{aligned}$$

In case we want to consider the elements of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ as infinity, we should consider the above correspondence valid for each element of the set A and for each element of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ consisting of an even number.

This means that the total number that can replace all the elements of the set A is the same number that can also replace all elements of set \mathbb{N}^* consisting of even numbers. However, since the elements of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ consisting of odd numbers have not been replaced, we can write:

$$tot(A) \neq tot(\mathbb{N}_{>0})$$

Let's now put the numbers of set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ and the pairs of numbers of set A in which the double of that value appears on the right in a one-to-one correspondence:

$$\begin{aligned}
1 &\leftrightarrow (1,2) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between 1 and 2} \\
2 &\leftrightarrow (3,4) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between 2 and 4} \\
3 &\leftrightarrow (5,6) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between 3 and 6} \\
&\dots && \\
n &\leftrightarrow ([2 \cdot n] - 1, 2 \cdot n) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between } n \text{ and } (2 \cdot n)
\end{aligned}$$

Always assuming the elements of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ as infinity, we should consider the above correspondence valid for each element of the set A and for each element of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$.

This means that the total number that can replace all the elements of the set A is the same number that can also replace all the elements of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$. We can then write the following relation:

$$tot(A) = tot(\mathbb{N}_{>0})$$

which contradicts the previous one. This certifies that all the elements of set A cannot at the same time exhaust all the elements of set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$, as the second correspondence tells us, and not exhaust them, as the first correspondence tells us instead.

Because the attribution of an infinite number of elements to the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ leads directly to a contradiction, we must necessarily attribute a non-infinite number of elements to it. The same of course must also apply to the set \mathbb{Z} which has twice the elements of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ plus the zero. □

4 Infinity in the case of rational numbers

Theorem 4.1. *The set \mathbb{Q} of rationals cannot have an infinite number of elements.*

Proof. Let's take a set A whose elements are obtained by gathering in pairs the elements of the set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$, the set of strictly positive rational numbers.

A possible set A that can be constructed is the following:

$$A = \{(1/2, 2/2), (3/2, 4/2), (5/2, 6/2) \dots, ([2 \cdot p] - 1)/q, [2 \cdot p]/q, \dots\}$$

where p, q are non-zero generic natural numbers, and therefore the value p/q

is a generic positive rational number, and where the pairs:

$$\begin{aligned} &(1/2, 2/2) \\ &(3/2, 4/2) \\ &(5/2, 6/2) \\ &\dots \end{aligned}$$

that constitute the individual elements of the set A include the rational number $[2 \cdot p]/q$, the double of each element p/q belonging to the set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$, and the rational number $[[2 \cdot p] - 1]/q$ with the same denominator, but with the numerator decreased by 1:

$$([[2 \cdot p] - 1]/q, [2 \cdot p]/q)$$

More simply we can write the set A in the following way:

$$A = \{([2 \cdot p] - 1]/q, [2 \cdot p]/q) \mid p, q \in \mathbb{N}_{>0}\}$$

Let's now put the numbers of the set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$ with even numerator and the pairs of numbers of the set A in which that total value appears on the right in a one-to-one correspondence:

$$\begin{aligned} 2/2 &\leftrightarrow (1/2, 2/2) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between } 2/2 \text{ and } 2/2 \\ 4/2 &\leftrightarrow (3/2, 4/2) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between } 4/2 \text{ and } 4/2 \\ 6/2 &\leftrightarrow (5/2, 6/2) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between } 6/2 \text{ and } 6/2 \\ &\dots && \\ [2 \cdot p]/q &\leftrightarrow ([2 \cdot p] - 1]/q, [2 \cdot p]/q) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\ &&& [2 \cdot p]/q \text{ and } [2 \cdot p]/q \end{aligned}$$

In case we want to consider the elements of the set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$ as infinity, we should consider the above correspondence valid for each element of the set A and for each element of the set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$ with even numerator.

This means that the total number that can replace all the elements of the set A is the same number that can also replace all the elements of the set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$ with even numerator. However, since the elements of the set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$ with odd numerator have not been replaced, we can write:

$$tot(A) \neq tot(\mathbb{Q}_{>0})$$

Let's now put the numbers of set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$ and the pairs of numbers of set A in which the double of that value appears on the right in a one-to-one correspondence:

$$1/2 \leftrightarrow (1/2, 2/2) \quad \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between } 1/2 \text{ and } 2/2$$

$2/2 \leftrightarrow (3/2, 4/2)$ \leftarrow the real correspondence is between $2/2$ and $4/2$
 $3/2 \leftrightarrow (5/2, 6/2)$ \leftarrow the real correspondence is between $3/2$ and $6/2$
 \dots
 $p/q \leftrightarrow (([2 \cdot p] - 1)/q, [2 \cdot p]/q)$ \leftarrow the real correspondence is between
 p/q and $[2 \cdot p]/q$

Always assuming the elements of the set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$ as infinity, we should consider the above correspondence valid for each element of the set A and for each element of the set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$. This means that the total number that can replace all the elements of the set A is the same number that can also replace all the elements of the set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$. We can then write the following relation:

$$tot(A) = tot(\mathbb{Q}_{>0})$$

which contradicts the previous one. This certifies that all the elements of set A cannot at the same time exhaust all the elements of set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$, as the second correspondence tells us, and not exhaust them, as the first correspondence tells us instead.

Because the attribution of an infinite number of elements to the set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$ leads directly to a contradiction, we must necessarily attribute a non-infinite number of elements to it. The same of course must also apply to the set \mathbb{Q} which has twice the elements of the set $\mathbb{Q}_{>0}$ plus the zero.

□

5 Infinity in the case of irrational numbers

Theorem 5.1. *The set \mathbb{I} of irrationals cannot have an infinite number of elements.*

Proof. Let's take a set A whose elements are obtained by gathering in pairs the elements of the set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$, the set of strictly positive irrational numbers.

Before constructing the set A , let's define the set I_B of base irrationals as any set of irrational numbers whose elements cannot be obtained from the other irrational numbers of that same set through multiplication by any rational number. For example, if we take the irrational number $\sqrt{2}$ as element of the set I_B , none of the following irrational numbers can belong to it:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(1/1) \cdot \sqrt{2} \\
 &(1/2) \cdot \sqrt{2} \\
 &(1/3) \cdot \sqrt{2} \\
 &\dots \\
 &(2/1) \cdot \sqrt{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&(2/2) \cdot \sqrt{2} \\
&(2/3) \cdot \sqrt{2} \\
&\dots
\end{aligned}$$

while, for example, the irrational number $\sqrt{3}$ can belong to it, since, as we know:

$$(p/q) \cdot \sqrt{2} \neq \sqrt{3} \quad \text{with } p, q \text{ any non-zero natural number}$$

If we take $\sqrt{3}$ as further element of our set I_B , none of the following irrational numbers can belong to it:

$$\begin{aligned}
&(1/1) \cdot \sqrt{3} \\
&(1/2) \cdot \sqrt{3} \\
&(1/3) \cdot \sqrt{3} \\
&\dots \\
&(2/1) \cdot \sqrt{3} \\
&(2/2) \cdot \sqrt{3} \\
&(2/3) \cdot \sqrt{3} \\
&\dots
\end{aligned}$$

If we take the following set of base irrationals whose elements include all strictly possible positive irrational numbers that cannot be obtained from the other irrational numbers of that same set through multiplication by any rational number:

$$I_B = \{i_1, i_2, i_3, \dots, i_k, \dots\} \quad \text{with } i_k > 0, k = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$$

it will suffice to multiply each of its elements by every possible strictly positive rational number in order to obtain the set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$ of strictly positive irrational numbers.

We are now able to construct the following set A :

$$\begin{aligned}
A = \{ &([1/2] \cdot i_1, [2/2] \cdot i_1), ([3/2] \cdot i_1, [4/2] \cdot i_1), \dots, \\
&([([2 \cdot p] - 1]/q) \cdot i_1, [[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_1), \dots, \\
&([1/2] \cdot i_2, [2/2] \cdot i_2), ([3/2] \cdot i_2, [4/2] \cdot i_2), \dots, \\
&([([2 \cdot p] - 1]/q) \cdot i_2, [[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_2), \dots, \\
&([1/2] \cdot i_b, [2/2] \cdot i_b), ([3/2] \cdot i_b, [4/2] \cdot i_b), \dots, \\
&([([2 \cdot p] - 1]/q) \cdot i_b, [[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_b), \dots, \}
\end{aligned}$$

where p, q are non-zero generic natural numbers, and therefore the value $[p/q] \cdot i_k$ is a generic positive irrational number expressed as a function of the

element i_k of the set I_B previously chosen, and where the pairs:

$$\begin{aligned}
& ([1/2] \cdot i_1, [2/2] \cdot i_1) \\
& ([3/2] \cdot i_1, [4/2] \cdot i_1) \\
& \dots \\
& ([1/2] \cdot i_2, [2/2] \cdot i_2) \\
& ([3/2] \cdot i_2, [4/2] \cdot i_2) \\
& \dots \\
& ([1/2] \cdot i_b, [2/2] \cdot i_b) \\
& ([3/2] \cdot i_b, [4/2] \cdot i_b) \\
& \dots
\end{aligned}$$

that constitute the individual elements of the set A include the irrational number $[2 \cdot p]/q \cdot i_k$, the double of each element $[p/q] \cdot i_k$ belonging to the set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$, and the irrational number $[[2 \cdot p] - 1]/q \cdot i_k$ expressed as a function of the same element i_k but multiplied by a rational number with the same denominator and the numerator decreased by 1:

$$([[(2 \cdot p) - 1]/q] \cdot i_k, [[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_k)$$

More simply we can write the set A in the following way:

$$A = \{([[(2 \cdot p) - 1]/q] \cdot i_k, [[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_k) \mid i_k \in I_B \text{ and } p, q \in \mathbb{N}_{>0}\}$$

Let's now put the numbers of the set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$ with even rational numerator and the pairs of numbers of the set A in which that total value appears on the right in a one-to-one correspondence:

$$\begin{aligned}
[2/2] \cdot i_1 &\leftrightarrow ([1/2] \cdot i_1, [2/2] \cdot i_1) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [2/2] \cdot i_1 \text{ and } [2/2] \cdot i_1 \\
[4/2] \cdot i_1 &\leftrightarrow ([3/2] \cdot i_1, [4/2] \cdot i_1) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [4/2] \cdot i_1 \text{ and } [4/2] \cdot i_1 \\
[6/2] \cdot i_1 &\leftrightarrow ([5/2] \cdot i_1, [6/2] \cdot i_1) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [6/2] \cdot i_1 \text{ and } [6/2] \cdot i_1 \\
\dots &&& \\
[[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_1 &\leftrightarrow [[(2 \cdot p) - 1]/q] \cdot i_1, [[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_1 && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence} \\
&&& \text{is between } [[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_1 \\
&&& \text{and } [[(2 \cdot p) - 1]/q] \cdot i_1 \\
\dots &&& \\
[2/2] \cdot i_2 &\leftrightarrow ([1/2] \cdot i_2, [2/2] \cdot i_2) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [2/2] \cdot i_2 \text{ and } [2/2] \cdot i_2 \\
[4/2] \cdot i_2 &\leftrightarrow ([3/2] \cdot i_2, [4/2] \cdot i_2) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [4/2] \cdot i_2 \text{ and } [4/2] \cdot i_2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
[6/2] \cdot i_2 &\leftrightarrow ([5/2] \cdot i_2, [6/2] \cdot i_2) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [6/2] \cdot i_2 \text{ and } [6/2] \cdot i_2 \\
\dots &&& \\
[[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_2 &\leftrightarrow [[(2 \cdot p - 1)/q] \cdot i_2, [(2 \cdot p)/q] \cdot i_2] && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence} \\
&&& \text{is between } [[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_2 \\
&&& \text{and } [[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_2 \\
\dots &&& \\
[2/2] \cdot i_b &\leftrightarrow ([1/2] \cdot i_b, [2/2] \cdot i_b) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [2/2] \cdot i_b \text{ and } [2/2] \cdot i_b \\
[4/2] \cdot i_b &\leftrightarrow ([3/2] \cdot i_b, [4/2] \cdot i_b) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [4/2] \cdot i_b \text{ and } [4/2] \cdot i_b \\
[6/2] \cdot i_b &\leftrightarrow ([5/2] \cdot i_b, [6/2] \cdot i_b) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [6/2] \cdot i_b \text{ and } [6/2] \cdot i_b \\
\dots &&& \\
[[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_b &\leftrightarrow [[(2 \cdot p - 1)/q] \cdot i_b, [(2 \cdot p)/q] \cdot i_b] && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence} \\
&&& \text{is between } [[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_b \\
&&& \text{and } [[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_b \\
\dots &&&
\end{aligned}$$

In case we want to consider the elements of the set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$ as infinity, we should consider the above correspondence valid for each element of the set A and for each element of the set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$ with even rational numerator.

This means that the total number that can replace all the elements of the set A is the same number that can also replace all the elements of the set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$ with even rational numerator. However, since the numbers of the set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$ with odd rational numerator have not been replaced, we can write:

$$tot(A) \neq tot(\mathbb{I}_{>0})$$

Let's now put the numbers of set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$ and the pairs of numbers of set A in which the double of that value appears on the right in a one-to-one correspondence:

$$\begin{aligned}
[1/2] \cdot i_1 &\leftrightarrow ([1/2] \cdot i_1, [2/2] \cdot i_1) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [1/2] \cdot i_1 \text{ and } [2/2] \cdot i_1 \\
[2/2] \cdot i_1 &\leftrightarrow ([3/2] \cdot i_1, [4/2] \cdot i_1) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [2/2] \cdot i_1 \text{ and } [4/2] \cdot i_1 \\
[3/2] \cdot i_1 &\leftrightarrow ([5/2] \cdot i_1, [6/2] \cdot i_1) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [3/2] \cdot i_1 \text{ and } [6/2] \cdot i_1 \\
\dots &&& \\
[p/q] \cdot i_1 &\leftrightarrow [[(2 \cdot p - 1)/q] \cdot i_1, [(2 \cdot p)/q] \cdot i_1] && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence} \\
&&& \text{is between } [p/q] \cdot i_1 \text{ and} \\
&&& [[2 \cdot p]/q] \cdot i_1 \\
\dots &&&
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
[1/2] \cdot i_2 &\leftrightarrow ([1/2] \cdot i_2, [2/2] \cdot i_2) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [1/2] \cdot i_2 \text{ and } [2/2] \cdot i_2 \\
[2/2] \cdot i_2 &\leftrightarrow ([3/2] \cdot i_2, [4/2] \cdot i_2) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [2/2] \cdot i_2 \text{ and } [4/2] \cdot i_2 \\
[3/2] \cdot i_2 &\leftrightarrow ([5/2] \cdot i_2, [6/2] \cdot i_2) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [3/2] \cdot i_2 \text{ and } [6/2] \cdot i_2 \\
\dots &&& \\
[p/q] \cdot i_2 &\leftrightarrow [[(2 \cdot p - 1)/q] \cdot i_2, [(2 \cdot p)/q] \cdot i_2] && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence} \\
&&& \text{is between } [p/q] \cdot i_2 \text{ and} \\
&&& [(2 \cdot p)/q] \cdot i_2 \\
\dots &&& \\
[1/2] \cdot i_b &\leftrightarrow ([1/2] \cdot i_b, [2/2] \cdot i_b) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [1/2] \cdot i_b \text{ and } [2/2] \cdot i_b \\
[2/2] \cdot i_b &\leftrightarrow ([3/2] \cdot i_b, [4/2] \cdot i_b) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [2/2] \cdot i_b \text{ and } [4/2] \cdot i_b \\
[3/2] \cdot i_b &\leftrightarrow ([5/2] \cdot i_b, [6/2] \cdot i_b) && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence is between} \\
&&& [3/2] \cdot i_b \text{ and } [6/2] \cdot i_b \\
\dots &&& \\
[p/q] \cdot i_b &\leftrightarrow [[(2 \cdot p - 1)/q] \cdot i_b, [(2 \cdot p)/q] \cdot i_b] && \leftarrow \text{the real correspondence} \\
&&& \text{is between } [p/q] \cdot i_b \text{ and} \\
&&& [(2 \cdot p)/q] \cdot i_b \\
\dots &&&
\end{aligned}$$

Always assuming the elements of the set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$ as infinity, we should consider the above correspondence valid for each element of the set A and for each element of the set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$. This means that the total number that can replace all the elements of the set A is the same number that can also replace all the elements of the set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$. We can then write the following relation:

$$tot(A) = tot(\mathbb{I}_{>0})$$

which contradicts the previous one. This certifies that all the elements of set A cannot at the same time exhaust all the elements of set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$, as the second correspondence tells us, and not exhaust them, as the first correspondence tells us instead.

Because the attribution of an infinite number of elements to the set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$ leads directly to a contradiction, we must necessarily attribute a non-infinite number of elements to it. The same of course must also apply to the set \mathbb{I} which has twice the elements of the set $\mathbb{I}_{>0}$ plus the zero.

□

6 Final considerations

The conclusion that we can draw from what we have seen is that if the cardinal numbers are not able to grasp the contradiction inherent in the notion of infinity is because they do not really capture the meaning of number of the elements of a set. And the easiest and most immediate way to reiterate it is to take the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ of natural numbers:

$$\mathbb{N}_{>0} = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 \dots\}$$

and observe how its cardinality ω remains unchanged even if we add further elements to it, as happens for example with the numbers 2,1,1,2 to form the following set C :

$$C = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 \dots, 2, 1, 1, 2\}$$

To identify the one-to-one correspondence between these two sets, it is sufficient to connect the last 4 numbers of C to the first 4 numbers of $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$:

$$\begin{aligned} 2 &\leftrightarrow 1 \\ 1 &\leftrightarrow 2 \\ 1 &\leftrightarrow 3 \\ 2 &\leftrightarrow 4 \end{aligned}$$

while for all the other numbers it's enough to go from n to $n+4$:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &\leftrightarrow 5 \\ 2 &\leftrightarrow 6 \\ 3 &\leftrightarrow 7 \\ \dots & \end{aligned}$$

The fact is that if changes in the number of elements of a set are not accompanied by changes in its cardinality, any possible isomorphism between these two concepts is lost. With the consequence that cardinality can no longer be interpreted as the number of elements of a set. This does not mean that cardinality is in itself an erroneous notion or that in putting two sets in a one-to-one correspondence we make some mistake. The error occurs only at the level of interpretation, and only in relation to what we believe to be happening between two sets put in one-to-one correspondence with each other.

If we want to attribute to the one-to-one correspondence between two sets the properties that it really possesses, we must consider it for what it is. That is, a rule that allows us to move uniquely from the elements of one set to those of another set. And that as such it needs an additional condition

to establish that the two sets considered have precisely the same number of elements. Which is that of a one-to-one correspondence occurring for all the elements involved.

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